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INVERTED ONLINE TEACHING TO MINIMIZE CONTACT IN PRACTICAL COURSES

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ABSTRACT

Inverted online teaching flips the classical method of online teaching, where students are taught at home by teachers in the lecture hall. In inverted online teaching the students come to the university and are connected to online supervisors. The students work at the experimental setups while cameras transfer the experiment during a video conference. The teachers observe and comment the student's actions. Core elements are 1. the shared screen, 2. the image of several mobile cameras and 3. the audio connection.

We carried out such a concept in the summer semester 2020 during practical courses and in Winter 2020/21 during supervision of Bachelor students. Additional instructional videos were offered explaining details of the experiment. Discussions and the final presentation of the results during a seminar were conducted online. In that sense students profit from university equipment while contacts are minimized.

1 INTRODUCTION: BLENDED LEARNING AND ONLINE TEACHING

During the Covid-19 pandemic home-lab experiments substituted closed laboratories and experimental classes. On the other side labs like the advanced practical courses in physics at Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg decided to offer experiments

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in presence of the students with a concept for the minimization of infection risks. Bachelor- and Master students must not be supervised online only in experimental subjects. When having students in the university other techniques need to be explored that allow for secure standards during a pandemic.

Online conferences became standard tools that formed our communication in 2020 and 2021. Teaching undergoes a transformation due to the digitalization. However, this is not new. The implementation of digital teaching into general higher education is understood as blended learning or online teaching since 20 years [1,2] and the idea of the flipped/ inverted classroom developed [3-9]. Stanford, UC Berkeley and the University of Michigan were the first offering own online teaching portals promoting blended learning as the future of the web 3.0.

Improved blended learning concepts extract the optimal and/or most advantageous elements from online teaching concepts leaving disadvantageous elements behind. Digital teaching does not necessarily need to substitute presence teaching [10-14]. We used blended learning elements during the Covid-19 pandemic substituting particularly those parts of practical courses with most personal contact like e.g. the accompanying seminar talks and discussion of experimental results aiming to work without both, without contact and without a loss of teaching quality. The flip was done partially, targeted to the desired learning outcome [15-18].

2 THE CONCEPT OF INVERTED ONLINE TEACHING

In the future, the requirements for online teaching and online communication will further increase. It is one of the basic skills of students to visualize, discuss and decide problems online. Therefore, it is necessary to share and communicate experimental problems which are difficult to access online in a suitable format. The idea of inverted online teaching helps students to work with the experimental setup but discuss the experiments on the internet via audio-visual equipment. In addition, experiments are made operable via remote access and students are supported with teaching videos. Inverted online teaching inverts the classical method of online teaching, in which students are taught at home by teachers in the lecture hall.

2.1 Elements of inverted online teaching.

During inverted online teaching the students sit directly at the experiments in the university and several cameras film the setup (see Fig. 1). The teachers observe the student's actions and can correct them, measured data can be discussed on shared screens. A suitable holder for the cameras allows the students to show details with good picture quality to the educators and move the camera freely between different elements of the setup. We use the open source software OBS (Open Broadcaster Software®) for the organisation of the different cameras on the shared desktop (see Fig. 1). Video conferences before and after the experiment are done with BBB (Big Blue Button®).

Fig. 1 example for inverted online teaching of the scanning electron microscope with camera and microscopy images (left side) and evaluation of the achieved resolution (right side).

Shared screen information and the shared camera are discussed in online conference style. This enables full supervision of the experiment and the evaluation without the physical presence of the teacher. The aim is a constant online presence. The concept enables more support with less effort and less physical contact.

Instruction in the software for recording or evaluating the measurement is done with short instructional videos and is then practiced online together. The videos are all hosted on the Youtube® channel of the experimental class [19]

2.2 Remote Experiments

A second line of inverted online teaching is the identification of selected experiments that can be done remotely. At the moment, we have set up Hall effect with a LabView® program that allows for the complete data acquisition, heating of the sample and measurements of current, voltage, temperature and Hall-voltage via Teamviewer®.

3 RESULTS AND EVALUATION

3.1 Online Seminar and Poster Presentation

We had very positive feedback from the students regarding online presentations during the seminar and poster presentations as part of their exam in the master's practical courses. 90 % of the students did not have problems to follow the presentations. However, we realized less activity during the online presentations as compared to the activity during the seminar in the lecture hall.

Fig. 2 Online Seminar and Online Poster Presentation during the practical courses.

3.2 Online Communication during experiments

The online communication during the experiments was not yet fully exploited. In spite of the fact that contact to the supervisors via video conference was established some students and supervisors preferred regular personal contact. The steady online conference to supervise the experimental work of the students was mainly executed during the supervision of Bachelor theses or with experienced students. At present (July 2021) we conduct teaching pupils following the concept of inverted online teaching with some selected pupils and/or students working on the electron microscope and supervisors as well as the rest of the study class observing the experiments from home or from school.

3.3 Evaluation results

The evaluation clearly showed that the students appreciated highly the possibility to work in the laboratory in presence. It even turned out that students agreed with the new structure of the advanced laboratory and the master's practical courses but they refused further digitalization of the practical courses. A complete digital practical course was refused by 80% of the students in contrast to the fact that 92% of the students did not have technical problems.

On a rating scale from 1 (very helpful) to 4 (not helpful) the students rated the available online documents and exchange of materials and protocols via email with best mark (1.3), however, this element was not new at all. The video conference and additional supporting teaching videos were rated with 1.6. In a range from 1 (very good) to five (very bad) the mixture of online components and presence experiments were rated with 2.0 however the didactical quality was only rated 2.4. This mark was considerably better than the rating of a completely digital experimental classes. The suggestion of pure online experiments was rated 4.0 (refused) with few exceptions (a few students rated the idea 1 or 2). The biggest advantage was seen in time flexibility and the biggest disadvantage was judged the feeling of being isolated from other students in the class.

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